

Rotavirus infection in 2D monolayer enteroid culture

Note1: for the reagents refer to “List of reagents for enteroid protocols” (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13847508)

Note2: Refer to protocol “Generation of 2D enteroid culture” (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13849461)

- 1) Prepare in a 48 well plate the 2D enteroids culture in Complete Medium expecting at least 4 well for each MOI
- 2) Start infection protocol after 48-72h, when the confluency is above 70%
- 3) Prepare the inoculum in microcentrifuge tubes using DMEM/F12 to dilute the viral stock at the desirable MOI
- 4) Activate RV inoculum in water bath for 1h at 37°C with 10 µg/ml trypsin
- 5) Dilute the inoculum with DMEM/F12 to reach a final trypsin concentration of 2 µg/ml or less
- 6) Wash the cells twice with PBSL
- 7) Add directly 200 µl/well of inoculum on the cell culture
- 8) Incubate for 1h at 37°C
- 9) Eliminate the inoculum (keep it at –80°C if needed for further analysis)
- 10) Wash twice the cells with PBSL
- 11) Add to each well 400ul of Complete Medium + 0,5 µg/ml trypsin
- 12) In order to follow the viral replication, collect for every MOI 200 µl of Medium (50 µl from each well of the same MOI) and keep it in -80°C.
Note: the collected supernatant is subjected to RNA extraction, followed by Real Time RT PCR for RV to monitor the viral load
- 13) Every 24h for at least 3 days of infection, collect for each MOI 200 µl of Medium and add fresh Complete Medium + 0,5 µg/ml to keep the cells with 350 µL of medium